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Deliverable D1.3 – Report on Co-creation with the extended CDTF

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WP1 - Co-design the ERA Hub model and KPIs

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List of abbreviation/Nomenclature

ACRONYM	STANDS FOR
CDTF	Co-Design Task Force
CZ	Czech Republic
D	Deliverable
DX.X	Deliverable Number
DK	Denmark
EC	European Commission
ERA	European Research Area
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
R&I	Research and Innovation
PLAYBOOK	COOPERATE Playbook
SA	Self-Assessment
TOOLBOX	COOPERATE Toolbox
NL	The Netherlands
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This deliverable entitled “D1.3 – Report on Co-creation with extended CDTF” provides insights and updated information on the sessions organised within COOPERATE Project engaging both the Co-Design Task Force and the extended one. Activities are coherent with the inverted funnel approach and have been developed in line with the Work Package 1, Task 1.2.

The report follows the order of the sessions, enabling the understanding of the evolution of the definition of the ERA Hub as well as the progress made in this regard, building on the feedback received from the Co-Design Task Force (CDTF) and the extended one. The latter has been engaged in the fourth phase of the inverted funnel approach, benefitting from international events such as the World Open Innovation Conference (WOIC), or the Inspiring ERA one. This co-creative bottom-up approach in (co)defining the ERA Hub allowed the COOPERATE Consortium to progress, while considering the perspective and needs of the players involved from each of the four helixes.

The co-creation sessions match the WP timeline, starting from M3 until M27. This second deliverable “D1.3 – Report on Co-creation with extended CDTF” collects all the data and information on the engagement of the CDTF and extended CDTF from January 2024 to March 2025. Information on the first year of activities (until December 2023) is available in the previous deliverable D1.2 “D1.2 – Report on Co-creation with the CDTF”

This document has been written by STAM, revised by IDEA Consult and TU/e, and approved by TU/e.

1 Introduction

The COOPERATE project operates within European Research Area (ERA) and the Pact for Research and Innovation (R&I) in Europe frameworks and considers the engagement with stakeholders – from professional and experts to civil society – a critical element of its comprehensive co-creation methodology in defining the ERA Hub concept. The initial Co-Design Task Force (CDTF) engages a select group of members of the COOPERATE Consortium and EuroTech Alliance within a specific area, while gradually expanding to a broader range of quadruple helix stakeholders, thus becoming the extended CDTF.

The sessions with the extended CDTF allowed the reflection and progress on the definition of the ERA Hub, while stimulating ahead thinking on the ERA concept and policy in a wider perspective.

The activities involving the extended CDTF were delivered within Work Package 1, under Task 1.2, which – above all – foresees the implementation of:

- 3 early hands-on co-creation arenas
- 3 co-creation validation workshops
- 3 hands-on co-creation arenas
- 4 virtual sessions

The early hands-on co-creation sessions took place in 2023, together with one co-creation workshop and one hands-on co-creation arena: report on these activities in available in Deliverable 1.2.

Consequentially, all the session carried out from M13 to M27 reflected on the initial takeaways from the co-creation activities in 2023 – among them:

- governance of the ERA Hub
- the Ecosystems Readiness Level (ERL)
- the barriers as well as strong points of the ecosystems

Based on the above-mentioned and following the “inverted funnel approach” the sessions were successfully organised and conducted with the targeted stakeholders’ groups. For a matter of clarity, the extended CDTF was mainly engaged in the three sessions aiming to validate and provide recommendations on the definition. Yet, this report also includes sessions with the initial CDTF as they all stimulated the progress and implementation of the definition.

Please note that two activities – the 3rd Hands on co-creation arena and the 4th Virtual session – will occur after March 2025.

2 Implementation of the inverted funnel approach in 2024

One of the key pillars of the COOPERATE project in developing and subsequently validating the ERA Hub model is represented by the engagement with stakeholders, through co-creation activities. Labelled Co-Design Task Force (CDTF), the latter groups together interested players from Eurotech Universities Alliance benefitting also from the presence of Technical Universities within the consortium, namely Technical University of Denmark, Technical University of Eindhoven and Czech Technical University in Prague.

From a general standpoint, and following the stages envisioned in the Grant Agreement, the co-creation sessions may be subdivided into two main clusters- such as “developing the reference model” and “full-fledge co-creation” – which, each in their turn, included other two steps. For a clearer understanding, [Figure 1](#) below provides a visualization of the co-creation stages.

Figure 1 - Co-creation stages

Building on the results and progress made in the first year of the COOPERATE project, the path in implementing the co-creation stages as well as the shift from the initial CDTF to the extended one proceeded as foreseen in the “Guidelines and planning for the co-creation activities and establishment of the CDTF” (2023), and in accordance with the “inverted funnel approach”.

This approach, further detailed into its stages as per [Figure 2 - Inverted funnel approach](#), mentions:

- The overall feature to be tackled (scoping, testing, co-creating with use-cases and communicating)
- The stakeholders involved (from consortium to extended CDTF)
- The type of activity (from co-creation to virtual sessions)
- The detailed objective of the activity (mission & thematic scope to recommendations and

communication)

The gradual opening from the CDTF to the extended one matches the above-mentioned approach, while supporting the inclusion of a broader range of stakeholders and fostering the collaboration among the quadruple helix actors.

Clearly enough, the broadening of the stakeholders involved, as well as the aim of the co-creation sessions reflect the progress of the definition of the ERA Hub, whose process considers both a bottom-up and top-down perspective. This ensures that the insights from stakeholders as well as policy guidelines and directives are equally and fully taken into consideration.

Figure 2 - Inverted funnel approach

3 From the initial Co-Design Task Force to the extended one

Before proceeding with the report on the co-creation activities, it is worth noting that players of the quadruple helix are already represented within the COOPERATE Consortium, giving it an initial push in developing a definition which balances the perspectives of all the four helixes, while also capitalising on the different experiences that these partners have within their R&I ecosystems.

As happened for the CDTF, also the extended CDTF includes interested parties while assuring geographical distribution, gender balance, thus guaranteeing inclusivity, diversity and a broader sharing of ideas. Figure 3 - CDTF and extend CDTF stakeholders shows the stakeholder groups, from CDTF to the extended CDTF.

Figure 3 - CDTF and extend CDTF stakeholders

Overall, the stakeholders targeted throughout the project are those listed in the “Guidelines and planning for the co-creation activities and establishment of the CDTF” (2023, p.9), horizontal to all the four CDTF, namely:

- Researchers and professionals in innovation;
- Innovation agencies, Regional Development Agencies, and Legal Entities overseeing ecosystems;
- Large enterprises, SMEs, and Industry associations;
- Policy organizations and government bodies at the EU, national, and regional levels;
- Other EU and regional initiatives, as well as ERA-related projects (e.g., Excellence Hubs);
- NGOs and Associations advocating for society, consumers, and the general public;
- Financial institutions, including banks and investors.

To maximise the possibility of engaging stakeholders – mainly CDTF EuroTech, broader CDTF (see Figure 3 - CDTF and extend CDTF stakeholders)– the inverted funnel approach is flexible enough to permit the movement from one stage to another, thus also allowing the participation to international events relevant to the COOPERATE project. Benefitting from this flexibility and to emphasise the evolution of the definition of ERA Hub, its changes and updates, this report will follow the chronological order of the activities with the CDTF and extended CDTF.

Table 1 below summarises the activities carried out in 2024; for those of 2023 please consult the Deliverable 1.2 “Report on the CDTF”.

<i>N.</i>	<i>Stage</i>	<i>Activity</i>	<i>Composition</i>	<i>Purpose</i>	<i>Timing</i>	<i>Venue</i>
1	Testing	Co-creation workshop	Consortium Eurotech CDTF	Testing initial concept	8 March 2024	Online
2	Communicating	Virtual session	Extended, broader CDTF	Validation and initial recommendations, concept mission piloting	5 June 2024	Prague (CZ)
3	Testing	Co-creation workshop	Consortium Eurotech CDTF	Testing revised concepts	25 June 2024	Online
4	Communicating	Virtual session	Extended, broader CDTF	Validation and initial recommendations piloting playbook and toolbox	19 September 2024	Brussels (BE)
5	Co-creating	Hands-on co-creation arena	Extended CDTF	Use cases with Czech, Danish and Dutch pilot	23 September 2024	Online
6	Communicating	Virtual session	Extended, broader CDTF	Recommendations, as well as ERA Hub definition and interplay playbook/toolbox and Self-Assessment for maturity levels	7 November 2024	Berkley (USA)

Table 1 - Sessions with stakeholders in 2024

Overall, the activities contributed to the achievement of the Key Performance Indicators as set out in the Grant Agreement of the project (see [Key Performance Indicators – status update](#)). By the time of writing eleven out of thirteen sessions have been completed, the remaining two are already planned as the Table 2 below.

<i>N.</i>	<i>Stage</i>	<i>Activity</i>	<i>Composition</i>	<i>Purpose</i>	<i>Timing</i>	<i>Venue</i>
7	Co-creating	Hands-on-co-creation arena	Extended CDTF	Call for Champions together with the 2 ecosystems for piloting II	April 2025	Online
8	Communicating	Virtual session	Extended, broader CDTF	Final event	May 2025	Online

Table 2 - Planned sessions with stakeholders in 2025

3.1 Testing the initial concept

After having completed the “scoping” phase, the co-creation session started to further investigate how to implement the definition of the ERA Hub. Building on the initial takeaways from the co-creation workshop in Lyngby (DK) in November 2023, the purpose of the second co-creation workshop – which took place online on 8th March 2024 - was to test the initial definition with the Consortium/Eurotech CDTF. The definition presented was the one below reported:

"ERA Hubs can be conceptualized as strategic platforms within the European Research Area (ERA) that aim to foster well-functioning R&I ecosystems by enhancing regional excellence, facilitated through knowledge transfer while serving as interfaces to promote interregional collaboration and learning across ecosystems."

Four main elements resonate in this initial definition, namely:

1. Strategic platform in the ERA,
2. Well-functioning,
3. Enhance regional excellence,
4. Knowledge transfer.

Starting from this definition, the intention was to further exchange with CDTF to see how to position the ERA Hub against other initiatives, such as European Digital Innovation Hubs (EDIHs), European Innovation Ecosystems (EIEs), Interreg Europe and Regional Innovation Valleys (RIVs).

From the audience, the question of whether this new initiative is needed on top of the existing ones remained a valid concern from some of the stakeholders, for example, on how this initiative related to the many others already in progress. Generally speaking, this specific ERA Hub initiative focuses on addressing gaps in the research landscape, particularly emphasizing the interaction between education, knowledge creation, and local R&I ecosystems. Nonetheless, the question above reported was shared and discussed also within the Consortium, as COOPERATE partners were also working to highlight the added value of it.

There are multiple initiatives, each claiming to address different aspects of research, knowledge transfer, and regional development. However, it is difficult to perceive how each initiative addresses specific problems or adds unique value. In this regard, as argued by some participants, while it was clear that knowledge transfer is important, the shift towards knowledge valorisation in European Commission discourse was also a point of discussion. In this regard, universities tend to prefer the term "knowledge transfer," but it is crucial to define who is responsible for what—whether it is knowledge valorisation, technology transfer, or something else entirely. Besides, as emerged during the workshop, universities often struggle to navigate the crowded field of EU-funded programs, and the overlaps between them create confusion.

In light of these initial inputs, further details were given by the Consortium, with special reference to the distinction between the Regional Innovation Valleys (RIVs) and the ERA Hubs. Thus, RIV is more region-focused, while ERA Hubs bring knowledge actors into the centre. The European Commission's Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (DG RTD) is supporting a new program considering these differing roles. The issue, however, is the lack of an overarching narrative to clearly communicate the differences and relationships between these initiatives. Besides, recalling what discussed above, the sector is indeed crowded, and for a new program to show added value, it must be transparent

about what it contributes to the R&I ecosystem.

While reflecting on the added value and the specificity of the initiative, a participant pointed out that one of the potential strengths of this initiative could be its focus on benchmarking and certification, providing evidence-based toolboxes that could differentiate it from other instruments. This approach could be particularly effective at both company and regional levels, allowing for tailored interventions based on a comprehensive analysis of a region’s needs. This could help clarify the landscape and create connections between existing programs, bridging gaps between different concepts and initiatives.

Building on the players involved, experts suggested to equally reflect on which are the stakeholders involved in the ERA Hub. As expressed from one participant, based on a concrete case on the RIV, the Basque region is actively participating, but the ERA Hub's stakeholders seem to include a broader range of actors, be they knowledge transfer offices (KTOs), technology transfer organizations (TTOs), and science and technology park. According to the expert, most likely, these entities are at the crossroads of research and innovation and may often find themselves already embedded in other initiatives, thus adding a layer of complexity in their participation to the ERA Hubs. Moreover, when reflecting on the target actors, TTOs – for instance – are mostly engaged in patenting activities, which yet seemed to be far from the definition.

In this regard communication appeared crucial. Hence, one participant raised the point of how having clear communication is paramount, particularly for individuals or organizations that are not fully familiar with EU instruments. Engaging a wider audience requires communication that is accessible and avoids jargon that might alienate non-experts. The challenge is to disseminate information in a way that appeals to a broader audience, ensuring that the message is not lost in the complexities of EU bureaucracy.

Despite the interesting conceptualisation of the model, participants underlined its vagueness. According to some of them, adding a paragraph to it to bringing it to a more practical level, to ease the understanding of what and ERA Hub is, would be beneficial. In addition, other expert joined the discussion suggesting to carefully reflect on the term “excellence” as it is a sensitive word at policy level: underlying the distance between “excellence” and “impact on research” would be advisable.

These ideas and inputs were duly considered and processed, leading the path towards other steps of the inverted funnel approach, and the definition of the ERA Hub.

<i>Name of the activity</i>	<i>Composition</i>	<i>Number of participants</i>	<i>Type of organisation</i>	<i>Geographic coverage</i>	<i>Date and place</i>
<i>Testing initial concept</i>	Consortium Eurotech CDTF	36	University, national agency, civil society organisation,	Belgium, Czech Republic, Danmark, Finland,	8 March

development agency, company	Italy, Spain, The Netherlands	2024, online
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Table 3 - Testing initial concept - participants data

3.2 Validation and initial recommendations, concept mission piloting

Following the testing of the initial concept, the next activity with the CDTF took place in Prague, Czech Republic, on 5th June 2024. Benefitting from the possibility of engaging with regional stakeholders, the session was open to the extended CDTF, allowing players involved in the Czech ecosystem to provide their inputs and feedback. The aim of this session was to validate the concept, while collecting recommendation to further progress with it. The definition presented at this meeting included the feedback received during the previous session: additional explanations were included in the definition to facilitate the understanding of the approach. In addition, further clarity was provided on the types of actors that would be targeted by the initiative.

“The ERA Hub is a central access point in providing a range of services with the ultimate goal to valorise knowledge & stimulate the flow of knowledge to foster regional excellence and improve inter-regional collaboration and learning”

- *The hub is based on a strong mobilisation of the competences/expertise already available within a particular region.*
- *Actors at the core of an ERA Hub are academia-based intermediaries including TTOs, KTOs, and university-based incubators that are operating at the interface between academic knowledge producers and other R&I actors.*

If, on the one hand, progress had been made in refining the definition, it remained too abstract according to some participants. Similarly to the previous session, the need to clarify the unique added value, brought by the ERA Hub, was further stressed. At the same time, although the ERA Hub is part of the third generation of innovation ecosystems, in some experts’ perspective, it faces challenges in defining its exact role and structure. Again, one significant concern was the lack of clarity on the involvement of TTOs. During the session, industrial partners also raised the question on how they could participate considering the lack of specific goals, and the vagueness of the definition.

Overall, the main takeaways of the session can be summarised in four main aspects:

1. In some countries, such as Czech Republic, the lack of a clear focus can hinder progress. Therefore, a more defined vision and subsequent strategies would be desirable;
2. The unique value proposition of the ERA Hub should be highlighted and made more explicit;
3. As the discourse also included innovation and growth, developing a long-term vision is essential for the sustainability of the initiative;
4. Trusting and collaborating relationships are also crucial – and somehow necessary conditions – to achieve a long-lasting impact.

A final remark regarding this first session engaging the broader CDTF: as the COOPERATE Consortium

is aware of the need to further stimulate the engagement of the whole players of the helix, this activity was also open to civil society, associations and other players beyond industry, academia and public authorities. Yet, most of the participants were from industry and/or academia.

<i>Name of the activity</i>	<i>Composition</i>	<i>Number of participants</i>	<i>Type of organisation</i>	<i>Geographic coverage</i>	<i>Date and place</i>
Validation and initial recommendations, concept mission piloting	Extended, broader CDTF	10	University, national agency, civil society organisation, development agency, consultancy company, SME	Belgium, Czech Republic, Denmark, Italy, The Netherlands	5 June 2024, Prague

Table 4 - Validation and initial recommendations, concept mission piloting - participants data

In the end, this definition was also further tested with Consortium Eurotech CDTF in the following co-creation workshop with the objective to collect further information and inputs.

3.3 Testing revised concepts

The second co-creation session organised online on 25th June 2024, built on the revised concept discussed in Prague, while engaging with the CDTF through interactive activities divided into four main blocks:

1. Revised definition of ERA Hubs (which was the same as the one in Prague)
2. The target audience
3. The added value
4. The positioning of the ERA Hub in relation to other initiatives

Starting with the first objective, according to some experts of the CDTF, it is important to clarify the role of ERA Hubs within the broader European landscape: the lack of a policy element may hinder its implementation. Yet, if one envisions the Hub as an independent "marketplace" model, the definition should then highlight its connection with the knowledge providers and potential beneficiaries.

Another reaction from the CDTF built on concrete experiences: an ERA Hub might also compete directly with regional clusters, especially in countries like Denmark, where clusters often operate within a "triple helix" model—collaborating across industry, government, and academia, but with a particular emphasis on industry leadership. Therefore, it would be valuable to distinguish between ERA Hubs and clusters more clearly.

At the same time, experts argued that when considering the "area", in the ERA Hub definition, it is essential to address its place-based nature. However, the question of whether the scope should be city-based, local/region-based, or even country-based remained open. Providing more details on this

would help stakeholders to understand the geographic and operational scope of the Hub. Meanwhile, regional excellence within the Hub and the criteria or measures of "excellence" should be defined more precisely, as further commented. Another participant also emphasised this aspect, tackling the way to measure the results generated by ERA hubs (e.g., regional excellence, inter-regional collaboration, and learning). Besides, participants also asked which would be the features of the ERA Hubs that would differentiate them from other initiatives (both organizational/structural and in terms of activities) to set ERA Hubs apart from other initiatives, and what unique value this specific configuration would bring.

Finally, participants wondered who the target of the service was, as well as who was the target of the central access point. In this regard, a dedicated part of the co-creation session was allocated to the topic of the target audience. As foreseen from the COOPERATE project, it addressed mainly KTOs and TTOs, together with university-based incubators, and academia-based intermediaries (see Picture 1).

Target audience of ERA Hubs

Knowledge valorisation organisations are at the core of an ERA Hub.

- **Focus:** Knowledge valorisation organizations that are committed to develop their R&I ecosystem and that are involved in activities facilitating knowledge valorisation and peer learning exercises
- **Target:** Knowledge Transfer Organisations (KTOs), Technology Transfer Offices (TTOs), university-based incubators, and academia-based intermediaries.
- **We do not target** public-private R&I connectors like incubators and accelerators, or science and technology parks, nor intermediaries linked to private sectors and corporates.

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Do you agree with knowledge valorisation organisations at the core of an ERA Hub?

Please indicate your name when commenting

Picture 1 - Testing revised concept - target audience

Yet, according to some participants, the evolution of single KTOs/TTOs into an ERA Hub seemed quite difficult, as they typically serve only one institution in most countries, they provide services to universities and spin-offs, but they lack a regional scope. The role of industry was also addressed by one participant: knowledge would primarily be disseminated to the public through products developed by industry, so excluding it may have some reverse effect.

Following the discourse on knowledge, during the session a dichotomy also emerged around the connection of ERA Hub to knowledge ecosystems, and its focus on R&I ecosystems. Hence, a question arose from the audience: how would ERA Hubs position themselves within those frameworks? Following the co-creation approach, it emerged that universities could also serve as an ERA Hub, according to some participants, while being very specific about the value added by ERA Hubs may also support the positioning process. This led to the final part of the workshop focusing exactly on the value

and positioning. Since these two aspects are closely related, the feedback received was interconnected. As further stressed, a clearer understanding of the added value of the initiative would help clarify its role and position in relation to other initiatives.

Name of the activity	Composition	Number of participants	Type of organisation	Geographic coverage	Date and place
Testing revised concept	Consortium Eurotech CDTF	26	University, civil society organisation, SME and industry, consultancy company, TTOs, academia	Belgium, Czech Republic, Denmark, Hungary, Italy, The Netherlands	25 June 2024, online

Table 5- Testing revised concept - participants data

The session following this one was held in Brussels (BE) within the mid-term event, addressing the extended CDTF, and targeting the validation and initial recommendation on toolbox and playbook, other two outcomes of the project.

3.4 Validating and initial recommendations piloting, playbook and toolbox

The COOPERATE mid-term event¹ hosted the second session with the extended CDTF, in Brussels on 19th September 2024 right after the High-level European Research Area Stakeholder Conference. Before starting the session, Mr. Patrick Brenier (DG RTD) provided an opening speech highlighting some key concepts, while setting the context of the ERA Hub framework.

The work conducted within both COOPERATE and ERA Fabric projects was presented in this session. Participants perceived both projects as being grounded in a robust and evidence-based methodology that was being tested and proven. Although the two projects follow different routes, a suggestion was made for an alignment in their terminology with the European Commission's (EC) standards to ensure consistency and effectiveness in the wider policy context. The development of joint policy recommendations by the two projects was also stressed, as this would enhance clarity for policymakers. In addition, looking ahead to 2025, deciding how to best leverage the results and outcomes of these projects remained a crucial aspect. One potential path foreseen was to elevate these tools to the level of a policy instrument, potentially tied to funding streams such as the FP (Framework Programmes) or excellence funds. Consequently, policy recommendations would thus be a fundamental output from both projects, inspiring the future direction of regional innovation policy efforts. The session then continued with exchanges with the extended CDTF, starting, as usual, with the definition of ERA Hub so far developed.

¹ The meeting was organised together with ERA Fabric project

Picture 2 - Session at mid-term event - definition of ERA Hub

The main feedback received during this session referred to the following aspects:

- First of all, although the seven lines of action was perceived as a positive starting point, more lines would be needed in more complex ecosystems.
- Second, participants ask for a more detailed and comprehensive account of the types of actors that would be involved in the ERA Hubs (e.g. explicit mentions to the research infrastructures or government funding agencies, etc.). Third, some participants inquired why ERA Hubs would focus on knowledge valorisation instead of innovation. As argued by a participant, innovation is a key driver in transforming ideas into tangible solutions, and thus the doubt on why prioritizing knowledge valorisation instead of innovation.
- Fourth, participants mentioned the difficulty in grasping the tangibility of ERA Hubs, wondering if this would be seen as a tool, a support mechanism, a network, a central node, or perhaps a combination of all. More information on the degree of overlap and synergies with existing initiatives would be required.
- Fifth, some participants stressed the need to reinforce the role of universities in innovation ecosystems.

The comments and feedback received from the extended CDTF were valuable and important to progress in the implementation of the project and the definition of ERA Hub.

<i>Name of the activity</i>	<i>Composition</i>	<i>Number of participants</i>	<i>Type of organisation</i>	<i>of Geographic coverage</i>	<i>Date and place</i>
<i>Validating and initial recommendations piloting, playbook and toolbox</i>	Extended, broader CDTF	43	University, civil society organisation, SME and industry, consultancy company, TTOs, academia	Austria, Belgium, Czech Republic, Denmark, Italy, The Netherlands	19 September 2024, Brussels

Table 6 - Validating and initial recommendations piloting, playbook and toolbox – participants data

The next co-creation arena addressed the piloting cases in Czech Republic, Denmark, and The Netherlands.

2.5 Co-creation with Czech, Danish and Dutch pilots

Held online on 23rd September 2024, the second hands-on co-creation arena focused on the piloting cases in Czech Republic, Denmark and The Netherlands, while initially defining the KPIs to measure the maturity of the R&I ecosystems. Before zooming into the main objective of the session, the COOPERATE Consortium illustrated the development of the definition, the concept of ERA Hub, and its main aspects.

Hence, according to the COOPERATE Consortium, the ERA Hub should not be a one-size-fits-all model, envisioning a flexible dimension in it to allow each ERA Hub to be tailored to the local characteristics of the region. As also emerged from the piloting, this was because each region has its unique set of characteristics and R&I ecosystems, which require bespoke approaches. Yet, as the Hubs are encapsulated within a broader European framework, there was also the necessity to have a common scale to measure the maturity of the R&I ecosystems, regardless of their region. To address this, the COOPERATE Consortium developed a five-point scale, ranging from "absence" to "advanced," with the objective that each R&I ecosystem would be able to measure the evolution of its maturity. Growth is crucial as it reflects the continuous improvement in the maturity of the Research and Innovation ecosystem. However, this scale can only be effective if the KPIs are meaningful and truly reflect the maturity of the R&I ecosystem; while stimulating the quadruple helix — bringing together government, industry, academia, and civil society – so that to jointly push forward. Finally, according to the Consortium, universities play a pivotal role in the process, acting as the central component.

Regarding the piloting activities presented, the [Table 7](#) below summarises the main takeaways, highlighting also the main challenges and the potential role of the ERA Hubs. The piloting activities involved three COOPERATE partners: CTU, DTU and TU/e.

<i>Pilot</i>	<i>Topic</i>	<i>Challenges</i>	<i>How the ERA Hub can support</i>
Denmark	Life science	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No sufficient in volume of talents to meet the industry demand • Lack of a life science IPO in many years • Despite the presence of some formal agreements and long-term partnerships, there are few tangible outcomes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overcoming the lack of a central player that has the overview and owns the joint agenda • Supporting initiatives to attract the very top international talent.
Denmark	Sustainable technology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Competitiveness of Denmark regarding e.g. Oxford and the Bay Area on top talent 	

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is a lot of political discourse and political awareness around sustainability but no coordinating point 	
The Netherlands	Semiconductor industry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Building and attracting talent • Low involvement of civil society • Scarce transfer of knowledge from previous projects/initiatives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support in securing talent and funding • Support specialization in regions through strengthening connections between these regions
The Netherlands	Health industry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low level in scaling of healthcare applications • Low data sharing and collection 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support the scaling by connecting regions • Assist with policy requirements
Czech Republic	Artificial intelligence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Absence of clear governance and commercialization pathways • Lack of tailored funding solutions for startups • Low enhancement of EU funding, standardized governance, and improved data access 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhances collaboration and governance • Support commercialization with targeted mentoring and funding • Expand access to EU and regional funding opportunities. • Develop skills through training and mobility programmes

Table 7 - Piloting activities takeaways

The experience in the pilots was presented together with the KPIs to measure the maturity of R&I ecosystems. Participants provided feedback while sharing their perspectives. One expert expressed some doubts about the extent to which the new concept of ERA Hub differs from other existing initiatives, especially in terms of thematic focus, and how it stands apart from initiatives, like clusters or thematic clusters, which already aggregate public, private, and civil society actors, and which also have a legal entity status. Hence, it was still unclear how ERA Hubs fit into the broader landscape of numerous initiatives across Europe and their own country. As emerged on other co-creation activities, also in this session participants underlined the need to further fine tune the added value of this concept.

Regarding the KPIs, another expert agreed with the notion that measuring the quantity of research is challenging, particularly since a publication does not necessarily reflect the same amount of research effort across different fields. At the same time, while understanding the need for quantitative metrics, in the perspective of one participant, grants awarded might serve as a more operational and

meaningful metric of quality, rather than quantity. As the discussion on the KPIs focused on a rather general level, due to time limits, experts were invited to take a closer look at the KPIs and provide their comments in a collaborative MIRO board available also after the end of the session. Figure 4 - Figure 4 - KPIs presented per line of actions_below lists the initial KPIs shared with the CDTF during the co-creation-session.

<p>Research</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Diversity of research areas: size of the universities (number of students); number of universities; faculties; degrees offered; of interdisciplinary research centres •Research outputs: Number of publications; of citations; share of open science publications •Research facilities: Are there infrastructures dedicated specifically to knowledge transfer activities?; Are there Research and Technology Organisations in the ecosystem?
<p>Talent</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Number of: employees involved in R&D activities in the ecosystem; PhD candidates in the ecosystem •Share of researchers with a foreign origin •Training opportunities: number of training programmes available in the ecosystem
<p>Knowledge transfer</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Are there key account managers responsible for managing relationships with other stakeholders in the ecosystem? •Are there academia-industry programmes for internships, mentorships and job placement opportunities in your ecosystem? •Number of workshops, hackathons and other informal knowledge sharing events involving at least one of the quadruple helix actors (excluding academia) •Average number of people attending these events •Does the ecosystem have in place communication lines in order to reach the desired audience?
<p>Funding</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Is there specific funding for R&I activities in the topic of your ecosystem? •Existence of funding streams for: basic research; proof-of-concept research; for testing and development; support commercialisation stages
<p>Collaboration</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Is there a single point of contact facilitating an effective coordination and communication between collaborators, streamlining processes and reducing potential barriers? •Are the parties involved associated through formal partnerships? If so, would you please indicate the type of partnership? •Which types of actors are active in this partnership?
<p>Governance</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Have the actors in the ecosystem developed a joint strategy for: R&I; Communication; Governance •Is there an evaluation system in place to quantify and track the progress and performance of the partnership? (Number of publications, patents, IPR development, policy recommendations, societal benefits) •Is there a clear division of roles and responsibilities between the actors involved in the ecosystem? •Are national/regional policy makers involved and committed in the ecosystem?
<p>Innovation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Are venture capital or angel investors active in your ecosystem? •Are there corporate partnerships active in R&I activities in your ecosystem? •Are there support programmes for startups (e.g. mentorships) in your ecosystem? •Number of: startup operating in the ecosystem; new startups created; patents filed; licensing agreements made

Figure 4 - Figure 4 - KPIs presented per line of actions

Name of the activity	Composition	Number of participants	Type of organisation	Geographic coverage	Date and place
Co-creation with Czech, Danish and Dutch pilots	Consortium Eurotech CDTF	23	University, civil society organisation, SME, industry, consultancy company, NGO	Belgium, Czech Republic, Denmark, Italy, Sweden, The Netherlands	23 September 2024, online

Table 8 - Co-creation with Czech, Danish and Dutch pilots - participants data

3.5 Validation, as well as ERA Hub definition and interplay playbook/toolbox and Self-Assessment for maturity levels

Following the progress made during the previous activities, the third validation session took place within the bigger World Open Innovation Conference (WOIC) framework, in Berkeley (USA) on 7th November 2024. Slightly different from the previous sessions with the extended CDTF, this meeting focused on the seven lines of action rather than the whole definition. Following a dynamic co-creative approach participants were given a set of questions divided per each line of action, to discuss and reflect upon. Benefitting from sticky notes, experts had the time to think about the response, write it down and the further exchange on it (see [Picture 3](#) as example below).

Picture 3 - Session at WOIC - canva on the line of action

The questions addressed during the session, for each of the seven lines of action were:

1. *Question 1: Which elements are needed for regional Research & Innovation Ecosystems to achieve this²?*
2. *Question 2: What can less advanced ecosystems do to achieve progress in this line of action?*

The discussion brought to the identification of the main takeaways on which to progress, according to each line of actions.

Starting with the line of action one “research”, according to participants, academic mobility and career growth structures (such as PhD and postdoc exchange programs) play a vital role in advancing expertise; while a sustainable funding models, like Norway’s government-funded research system, ensure the long-term relevance of research. In addition, if on the one the one hand, a balance between diversity and specialization represents a needed element to generate high-quality research; on the other hand, spurring group efforts over individual achievements favours collaborative research. One last comment addressed policies: those that address language matters should highlight accessibility and regional relevance, balancing English with local languages.

Regarding the second question, partnerships are crucial to enable open data sharing and build specialized research clusters for less advanced R&I ecosystems. Equally, based on the extended CDTF notes, translating basic research into applied solutions is facilitated by stronger industry partnerships. National and international networking events can foster collaboration, while improving education quality and cross-disciplinary cooperation is essential to developing a robust research environment.

Moving to the second line of action, aiming at developing an attractive destination for talent, four main elements were considered crucial:

1. Hosting cultural and community-building initiatives, such as festivals to encourage regional appeal
2. Fostering industry opportunities while communicating narratives of regional successes
3. Enhancing initiatives to support the transition among different sections, such as from academia to industry
4. Investing in competitive benefits for talents, be they housing, salaries etc.

Looking at less developed R&I ecosystems, according to participants, the steps to be taken regarding “talents” stretched from creating programs that attract and retain talent (e.g., exchange programs, corporate-academia rotations) to fostering a supportive R&I ecosystem culture. This also included further and broader actions, such as developing targeted advertising on regional strengths and unique opportunities, while supporting community integration and networking for foreign and local talents. On a final note, according to experts, engaging diaspora communities in national research projects could also represent a valuable action to implement when addressing talents.

² “this” refers to the line of action addressed, thus: research, talent, knowledge transfer, funding, governance, collaboration and innovation

As for the research line of action, also in the case of the third one “Knowledge Transfer”, policies play a key role in the process, particularly those encouraging research mobilization (e.g., industrial PhDs, student mobility). Yet, participants also saw the need to have a centralized organization to coordinate both the networking and knowledge transfer, while keeping separated the role of universities and broader R&I ecosystems. The former are thus considered crucial for research and incubation, while the latter for acceleration and commercialization.

For a less advanced R&I ecosystem, the needed elements that emerged from the session mainly built on the relationship between academia and industry. Hence, structured platforms for knowledge exchange may be valuable to be implemented, as well as creating either in-person or digital collaboration channels. Temporary placements represent an opportunity to enable industry experience for academic professionals, as well as offering match-making services between startups, SMEs, and experts. On a closing note, mentorship programmes engaging retired industry professionals for knowledge sharing with startups could also increase the knowledge transfer among less advanced R&I ecosystems, as mentioned by one participant.

To help ensure the availability, visibility, and access to relevant funding options to sustain the potential of the R&I ecosystem from research to market (referring to line of action 4 “funding”), participants of the session highlighted the establishment of private-public partnerships – be they government funding, venture capital, corporate sponsorship – as key element, together with focus areas to attract venture capital investment. In addition, two other considerations have been made in relation to personnel: training courses to increase awareness and literacy on funding should be implemented, while dedicated personnel should also be involved for funding, sponsorship, and investor engagement. Remaining within this line of action, five aspects have been considered for less advanced R&I ecosystems:

1. Improving transparency while simplifying grant processes
2. Consolidating funding information through the creation of a centralised digital platform
3. Fostering cross-regional and interregional collaboration
4. Involving diaspora in investment and partnerships
5. Attracting large investors by the development of first-mover advantages

As already mentioned in other lines of action, such as “talents”, to foster sustainable collaboration (line of action 5) in R&I ecosystems, it is essential to create regular events that connect researchers, industry, and policymakers. Based on the extended CDTF perspective, engaging players of the helix represents a twofold value: building relationships and enabling knowledge exchange, while promoting “coopetition” (cooperation among competitors). The latter may have a positive spillover effect on minimising regulatory barriers. In addition, establishing platforms for long-term project coordination ensures that the collaboration persists beyond short-term goals.

In less advanced R&I ecosystems, participants suggested several options: from organizing ecosystem-wide events to increase visibility and attract a wide range of stakeholders; to mentorship programmes,

to stimulate growth and innovation. The establishment of ecosystem clusters, which target specific industries or innovation areas, addressing local needs and encourage specialization could likewise be considered as a valuable element to implement. Finally, to better collaboration, bureaucratic limitations that hinder flexibility should be addressed.

Governance represented the sixth line of action and effective governance is crucial for R&I ecosystems. In this regard, the creation of a non-profit or central governing entity that facilitates communication and cooperation among stakeholders has been suggested by participants. At the same time, they also advised for a transparent organizational structure with clear goals, metrics (such as KPIs), and specific focus areas for each region; while promoting a culture of "giving back" to the R&I ecosystem could facilitate shared success and encourage further growth.

For less advanced R&I ecosystems, some feedback received recalled the essentiality to develop incubators, accelerators, and targeted support for early-stage startups, and to focus on regional strengths and/or industry expertise. Benefitting from concrete insights and knowledge from participants, looking to successful governance models, such as those in Chicago or Melbourne, could similarly offer valuable insights. As occurred for the more advanced R&I ecosystems, also in this case encouraging risk-sharing and promoting a "give-back" culture within the R&I ecosystem could help the creation of a collaborative environment.

Finally, regarding the seventh line of action, namely innovation, extended CDTF identified key needed elements, which can be grouped in the below-listed elements:

1. Alignment among professional incubation systems and industry requires
2. Policies that allow student ownership of intellectual property (IP)
3. Facilitation of knowledge transfer and innovation benefiting from the support for cross-sector programs
4. Public recognition to drive demand for new technologies
5. A centralised orchestration that governs
6. Availability of talents and students

Meanwhile, the feedback received for the less advanced R&I ecosystems were summarised in seven main aspects:

1. Building trust and understanding among R&I ecosystem actors
2. Encouraging industry-university partnerships to accelerate applied research and commercialization
3. Establishing annual awards to celebrate innovation achievements
4. Providing entrepreneurship training and financial support from government sources, with special regards to specific programmes for PhD candidates
5. Promoting co-creation activities with diverse actors at early stages to define needs

This was the last session engaging either the initial CDTF or the extended one. The remaining two

sessions will be implemented from April 2025 to June 2025.

<i>Name of the activity</i>	<i>Composition</i>	<i>Number of participants</i>	<i>Type of organisation</i>	<i>Geographic coverage</i>	<i>Date and place</i>
<i>Validation, as well as ERA Hub definition and interplay playbook/toolbox and Self-Assessment for maturity levels</i>	Extended, broader CDTF	18	University, civil society organisation, SME and industry, consultancy company, TTOs, academia	Austria, Belgium, Czech Republic, Denmark, USA, The Netherlands	7 November 2024, Berkley

Table 9 - Validation as well as ERA Hub definition - participants data

4 Conclusion and way forward

This deliverable entitled “Report on the co-creation with the extended CDTF” illustrates the progress made in developing the definition of the ERA Hub from January 2024 to March 2025 through the co-creation sessions. This series of sessions opened to the extended CDTF, engaging with different stakeholders from the quadruple helix and addressing different aspects of the concept. With regards to the fourth helix, the COOPERATE Consortium will further encourage the participation of the civil society in the remaining two sessions.

Together with the feedback received during the interviews and in the piloting activities, the consortium partners have made progress in the definition of the ERA Hubs concept from different perspectives:

- **Concept boundaries:** this refers to scope of the ERA Hubs definition, which aspects of R&I should be addressed and why.
- **Actors involved:** stemming from the previous point, the ERA Hubs definition would need to clearly define the types of actors that would be involved in the ERA Hubs.
- **Political vision and objectives:** this point makes reference to the alignment of ERA Hubs with the higher-level political goals of the European Commission and the Member States.
- **Applicability:** this refers to the need of developing an ERA Hub concept that resonates and has potential to be applied across the 27 Member States, in different thematic areas and in regions with varying degrees of ecosystem maturity.
- **Synergies:** this points to the need of avoiding unnecessary overlaps with existing initiatives and looking for synergies with relevant frameworks and policy actions.
- **Operationalisation:** this last point makes reference to the measurability of the ERA Hubs and their progress over time, as well as the mechanisms to establish connections and collaboration between ERA Hubs.

Therefore, the definition substantially changed from the initial version to the updated one – as indicated in the [Figure 5](#) below.

ERA Hubs become more clearly rooted on the need to foster knowledge valorisation within the regions, led by universities as main creators of knowledge and with the participation of quadruple helix actors. The concept becomes more “operational” as it focuses on setting up a core team of professionals representing the quadruple helix actors within the R&I ecosystem and meeting regularly with a clear agenda centred on knowledge valorisation. By discussing and agreeing on the priorities for the R&I ecosystem, these meetings can help to structure collaboration and enhance knowledge valorisation outputs in the regions.

More information on the concept and its different facets, reflecting the inputs gathered through the Phase II piloting activities and the last two cocreation sessions, will be provided in the White Book (Deliverable 4.4).

Figure 5- Evolution of the ERA Hub definition

5 Key Performance Indicators – status update

Table 11 - Detailed data on the phases by M27 and [Table 11](#) show the main data recorded within the M13 (January 2024) and M27 (March 2025) of project implementation. The KPIs as per Grant Agreement are reported on the left column of Table 10 - KPIs and Data at M27, while the right one provides updates by M27. As in the previous deliverable, [Table 11](#) provides information regarding the composition of the CDTF and the geographic coverage, as per the Guidelines mentioned in the section

1.1.

<i>KPIs to reach as per Grant Agreement</i>	<i>Indicator status at M27</i>
<i>30 active participants from Eurotech members in the CDTF Task Force</i>	44
<i>90 individuals during the co-creation stages</i>	69
<i>3 early hands-on co-creation arenas</i>	Done
<i>3 co-creative validation workshops</i>	Done
<i>3 hands-on co-creation arenas</i>	2 done, 1 planned after M27
<i>4 virtual sessions mobilising a broad community of stakeholders</i>	3 done, 1 planned after M27

Table 10 - KPIs and Data at M27

Name of the activity	Composition	Number of participants <i>(some joined in more than one activity)</i>	Type of organisation	Geographic coverage
<i>Co-creation workshop</i>	Consortium Eurotech	62	University, civil society organisation, SME and industry, consultancy company, TTOs, academia, national agency, development agency	Belgium, Czech Republic, Denmark, Hungary, Italy, The Netherlands Finland
<i>Hands-on co-creation arena</i>	Consortium Eurotech CDTF	23	University, civil society organisation, SME and industry, consultancy company, TTOs, academia	Belgium, Czech Republic, Denmark, Hungary, Italy, The Netherlands
<i>Virtual session</i>	Extended, broader CDTF	87	University, civil society organisation, SME and industry, consultancy company, TTOs, academia	Belgium, Czech Republic, Denmark, Hungary, Italy, The Netherlands, The USA

Table 11 - Detailed data on the phases by M27

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